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Abstract

As one among the core missions towards the realization of nuclear fusion, a future reactor must provide efficient and safe power exhaust through both divertor and first wall (FW). Recent studies have confirmed that the greatest challenges arise from the occurrence of plasma transients. Indeed, extensive damage of the plasma facing component (PFC) may occur during transients, with the risk of loss of coolant accidents (LOCA) that would hinder the safety of a future reactor as well as its prompt return to normal operation. Among the possible wall protection strategies, a sacrificial and micro-engineered surface made of porous tungsten (W) may promote the heat flux reduction while preventing the failure of the cooling pipe. As a preliminary step in this direction, the present study aims to investigate the possible application of W-based open cell foams as a sacrificial armor material. At first, an equivalent solid model, originally validated for Al open cell foams, was transferred to W foams. Then, a steady state thermal FEM analysis was carried out to evaluate the equivalent thermal conductivity provided by several foam configurations. Ultimately, a scaling law of the thermal response was developed as a function of the most influential foam parameters. As a future outlook with respect to DEMO-relevant transients scenarios, the scaling law will support design optimization and tailoring of an advanced FW PFC provided with a sacrificial W foam armor.

Keywords: DEMO, plasma facing components, heat load, protection strategy, open-cell foam, FEM analysis

1. Introduction

The heat and particle exhaust inside a tokamak is currently regarded as one of the most challenging missions for nuclear fusion [1]. Divertor and first wall PFCs are subject to severe heat flux, erosion and sputtering together with additional limitations owing to the presence of a neutron flux [2]. Considering DEMO and future reactors, even harsher conditions are expected. Recent studies have disclosed that the greatest challenges arise from the occurrence of plasma transients, such as plasma limited phases, vertical displacement events (VDE) and disruptions [3]. A DEMO-like upward unmitigated VDE TQ was simulated assuming a plasma thermal energy content of 1.3 GJ and a SOL broadening factor equal to 7, in accordance with [4]. The resulting power densities onto

the FW are in the order of several tens of GW/m² for the 4 ms of deposition time considered. As a result of these extreme heat loads, severe damage is expected due to surface vaporization, melting and re-solidification. An eventual failure of a standard FW concept [5] may result in LOCA accidents hence compromised reactor safety and delayed return to normal operation. Therefore, wall protection strategies are needed to mitigate or avoid failures. Among the many, we can mention the gas protection, including vapor shielding, recently investigated by S. Pestchanyi et al. [6]. The impinging heat flux could be lowered up to 8 – 10 times by vapor shielding. The liquid coolant protection can also be mentioned as an effective strategy, where the energy deposition is mitigated by a flowing sacrificial layer of coolant/breeder liquid.

In addition to extrinsic strategies, one may think to provide the plasma with a sacrificial layer that promotes

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the heat flux reduction by material degradation, that involves the benefits of both the above mentioned strategies. Micro-engineered structures can be tailored to allow a proper spreading of the thermal stress onto a larger volume thus preventing the failure of the cooling pipe. Although targeting inertial fusion energy (IFE) FW applications, a number of possible W-based micro-engineered armors, such as micro-machined structures, plasma-sprayed coatings, lattice structures and foams are described in [7].

Metal foams are a class of materials with low density and novel thermo-physical properties [8]. Since the middle of last century, their market penetration has been driven by the need for high performance, lightweight structures tailored for functional requirements, e.g. energy absorption, heat exchange and thermal management. Foams admit plastic deformation of cells and ligaments, leading to relieved stress levels and hindered brittle crack propagation [9]. In addition, their quasi-volumetric energy adsorption allows load spreading over larger areas and deeper inside the structure, rather than only on the top surface, at the same time offering a shielding effect to the underlying areas. However, the macroscopic behavior of foams derives from several parameters, e.g. cell and ligament geometry, anisotropy, pore density (measured in pores per inch, ppi). An additional key parameter is the relative density $\bar{\rho}$, defined as the ratio between solid volume V_s and total volume V , but also related to density ρ and porosity p

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{V_s}{V} = 1 - p \simeq \frac{\rho}{\rho_s} \quad (1)$$

Work on carbon and refractory foams for fusion applications has been ongoing for over three decades. Pioneering work on carbon foams have been carried out by D. L. Youchison [10]. However, carbon cannot be regarded as a relevant armour material for DEMO due to tritium retention and erosion. Chemical vapour deposition (CVD) was performed by Ultramet to apply thin W coatings on skeletal structures made of carbon, TaC or SiC [11]. W coated foams have been used as heat transfer enhancer in most of the cases: a number of helium cooled divertor mock-ups with internal foam inserts have been proposed [12]. Among them, an integrated refractory structure combining a W pipe with an internal skeletal structure of inter-connected ligaments coated with CVD W has survived a maximum absorbed heat flux of 22.4 MW/m² [13]. As described in [12], to cope with thermo-hydraulic optimization of these components significant efforts in advanced modeling and CFD analysis were involved, even converting x-ray

micro-tomography results into 3D stereo-lithography models. M. Andersen et al. used a 3D Kelvin cell geometry with 80×20×20 μm square sectioned ligaments to design an open cell W foam having near 10% of relative density and 100 ppi [14]. Although targeting IFE applications, its thermo-mechanical response as armour material was assessed, taking material properties and loading/cooling conditions from [7]. The foam proved to be a promising armour material, having mitigated interface mismatch, low thermal stress and enhanced helium release. However, the use of sharp edged ligaments led to overestimated temperatures and only the mechanical validation was carried out.

With the present study, we aim to develop an equivalent and parametric model for W foams, together with a scaling law of its thermal characteristics. These preliminary results will be instrumental to assess the thermo-mechanical behavior of tailored W foam armours to be used as sacrificial protection strategy during DEMO unmitigated disruptions.

2. Equivalent and parametric solid model

We relied on a 3D model originally developed and validated by P. Fanelli et al. for Al open cell foams [15]. As shown in Figure 1, a detailed shaping of ligaments and nodes of the Kelvin cell can be tuned, starting from literature and experimental evidences, in terms of:

1. Ligament length, L
2. Ligament reference cross section area, A_0
3. Cross section profile, $f(\xi)$
4. Cell anisotropy, λ

L is a key parameter impacting pore density and relative density. This latter is also affected by the cross section area along the ligament, provided by Yang [16]

$$A(\xi) = A_0 \cdot f(\xi) = A_0(36\xi^4 + \xi^2 + 1) \quad (2)$$

where $A(\xi)$ is the cross section area at a dimensionless axial position ξ . Concerning Al foams, the conventional manufacturing routes typically lead to triangle-shaped cross section areas [16]. However, the use of circular ones in the present model does not affect the similarity [15]. Cell anisotropy, instead, is the ratio between height and width of the Kelvin cell. The advantage of a parametric approach is dual: if transferable to W, this model could be either tuned on available measurements or used for design optimization. Thus, while tomography was left as back-up option to cope with real foam geometries, the transferability of this model to W was investigated to exploit the beneficial capability of designing tailored structures.

Figure 1: Some cell variants of the existing model

Figure 2: Temperature distribution after model calibration

3. Scaling law development

In the Fourier equation, thermal diffusivity α appears to be the key parameter during fast transients. Thermo-physical properties of solid W are available in literature [17], thus thermal diffusivity of a porous material can be expressed as a function of its relative density $\bar{\rho}$ and thermal conductivity k :

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{\bar{\rho} \rho_s c_{p,s}} \quad (3)$$

where $c_{p,s}$ and ρ_s are the specific heat and density of the solid material. At first, the transferability of the above described 3D model was confirmed through model calibration with respect to a reference study [7]. Initially, k was assumed as a function of $\bar{\rho}$ and a material index C , as suggested in [8]:

$$\frac{k}{k_s} = \bar{\rho}^C \quad (4)$$

with k_s referred to the solid material. Then, our model was scaled in order represent a foam having 100 ppi and approximately 8% of relative density. The cross section profile and cell anisotropy were kept as in [15]. In

accordance with [14], a 0.8 mm thick foam layer was bonded to a 3 mm thick heat sink made of F82H RAFM steel. The resulting volume was then meshed with a total of 12763 *solid* elements and approximately 25000 nodes. Material properties as a function of temperature were taken from [17] (T in K for F82H, $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for W)

$$k_{F82H} = T(0.21 - 4.96e-4 T + 4.98e-7 T^2 - 1.84e-10 T^3)$$

$$k_W = 174.93 - 0.11 T + 5.01e-5 T^2 - 7.83e-9 T^3$$

As mentioned in [7], the cooling channel is located at the rear surface of the heat sink, where helium flows at 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 10 MPa and 50 m/s. To ensure the similarity, the same heat transfer coefficient of 10000 $\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$ was considered, although lower values are obtained using HEPROP. Instead, the heat flux \dot{q} was applied to the top surface of the foam, called A_{exp} . Its value can be defined such to allow the analogy with the reference study, for which the heat exhausted by the heat sink, called \dot{q}_{eff} , can be evaluated. Through the following power balance, where also the cross section area of the heat sink A_{hs} appears, a proper value of \dot{q} was calculated

$$\dot{q}A_{exp} = \dot{q}_{eff}A_{hs} \quad (5)$$

The resulting temperature gradient in Figure 2 appears in tight agreement with the reference, with a relative difference between maximum temperatures of 0.25%. This confirms the applicability of our model to W foams. In addition, k is 5.62 W/mK , in agreement with the reference and existing thermal measures carried out by Ultramet on similar W foams.

As a further step, it was decided to extrapolate a parametric law for the thermal characteristics of foams having different geometrical features. Several combinations of ligament length L and reference cross section A_0 were investigated, the former ranging between 0.15 – 0.23 mm, the latter between $1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm^2 . For each combination, a regression analysis was carried out, resulting in linear trends with respect to A_0 . The influence of L was then taken into account through polynomials respectively fitting the slope $m(L)$ and intercept $n(L)$ coefficients, shown in Figure 3 and reported below.

$$m(L) = -1.78e4 L^3 + 1.23e4 L^2 - 3.00e3 L + 2.76e2$$

$$n(L) = 5.16e2 L^3 - 2.41e2 L^2 + 20.47 L + 2.65$$

Consequently, we could reshape $\bar{\rho}$ in order to include the impact of the chosen foam parameters:

$$\bar{\rho}(A_0, L) = 100 \cdot A_0 \cdot m(L) + n(L) \quad (6)$$

Figure 3: Coefficients for the regression analysis of $\bar{\rho}$

Figure 4: Dependence of k on $\bar{\rho}$ (a), L and A_0 (b)

As observed, a significant increase in density seems to be possible with increasing A_0 , and apparently this increase is even more pronounced at low L . Concerning the material index C , a refined formula was achieved starting from the correlation between k and $\bar{\rho}$, in Figure 4a. By comparing that formula with eq. (4), after few steps the following expression was obtained

$$C(A_0, L) = 1.1758 - \frac{\ln[k_s/108.4167]}{\ln[\bar{\rho}(A_0, L)]} \quad (7)$$

Ultimately, by replacing eq. (6) and (7) in eq. (4), a scaling law representing the thermal behavior of W-based open cell foams was achieved as a function of influential foam parameters:

$$k [W/mK] = k_s \cdot \bar{\rho}(A_0, L)^{C(A_0, L)} \quad (8)$$

The proposed scaling law offers the advantage of being theoretically applicable to a broad range of porous materials and it will be instrumental, together with the solid model itself, to cope with DEMO relevant thermo-mechanical assessments. While the solid model can be used for three-dimensional analysis, the scaling law provides smeared properties depending on constitutive features and operating temperature only. In Figure 4b, values of k obtained from the above described analysis are presented. They range between

2 and 12 W/mK, with the highest ones resulting from the combination of high A_0 and low L , as mentioned. This suggests that a sacrificial W foam armor up to few mm of thickness might offer acceptable performances during normal operation while experiencing material degradation during disruptions in order to prevent more severe damages.

On the other hand, a number of simplifying hypothesis has been assumed. For instance, the mirror boundary implied in the thermal analysis discounts any lateral heat conduction. Its impact is indeed negligible during steady state. However, even during fast transients we expect that the heat diffusion is too low, steep and shallow that only the wetted area should be interested, with only marginal lateral diffusion. As a further assumption, we speculate that equivalent properties coming from the scaling law are also valid during transients and locally. About this latter, as conductivity of solid W appears in eq. (8), we found that porous and solid material share the same qualitative degradation in temperature, even if increasing porosity leads to lower values at a given temperature. Furthermore, real cell structures are typically irregular and anisotropic. Therefore, experimental validation and material characterization are mandatory to evaluate the effectiveness of tuning a regular Kelvin cell on real measures, at least to identify representative volume elements. About this, experiences on W fuzz characterization already exist, as mentioned in [13], so they would result supportive during foam characterization. Ultimately, such complex W structures may require advanced manufacturing routes, such as additive manufacturing [18], that should be preferred to conventional techniques.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, the potential application of W foams as sacrificial wall protection strategy for future reactors is investigated. As a preliminary achievement, the scaling law of the thermal characteristics of W based open cell foams has been developed starting from a solid model originally validated for Al foams. Transferability to W was confirmed through model calibration with a reference study. The scaling law of the thermal characteristics of W foams was then obtained by including the effect of the most influential parameters, allowing design optimization and tailoring for functional requirements.

Main outlook of this activity is to anticipate thermo-mechanical assessment of W foam armors under the ex-

treme heat fluxes expected during DEMO unmitigated disruptions. On this regard, the established solid model and scaling law will be instrumental, allowing us to perform both smeared and three-dimensional evaluations. On the other hand, material characterization and further validation are needed. Conventional manufacturing technologies of W may represent a limitation to design optimization.

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